

*Problems in translating metaphors used in world literature and ways to
overcome them*

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Annotation: Although sufficient research has been conducted on metaphor in linguistics, interest in it is growing. Because in order to use words in the language, it is necessary to know the meaning of the words as well as their figurative meanings. This, in turn, means that there is a need to comprehensively study metaphor in linguistics. After all, linguists connect research on the science of metaphor with the manifestation of metaphor in linguistics and its importance in language.

Key words: literature, problems. metaphors, translation, research.

It is known that portable meanings are specific to words and are only experienced in speech. Therefore, they are referred to as colloquial portable meanings. This type of portable meaning in words is called portable meaning, formed in linguistics on the basis of metaphor – analogy. As we describe the studies studied on metaphor in this part, we first turned to the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language”. Metaphor [yun. metaphora-displacement, displacement] is the use of a word or phrase in a portable sense based on similarity or analogy, and the use of a word or phrase in such a sense; istiora, figurate (mas, dutorning of the word ear its meaning in ear combination arose on the basis of metaphor) Hence, metaphor means displacement, displacement. Thinkers of the ancient world have also expressed their attitudes towards metaphor. For example, the Greek thinker Aristotle viewed any word used in a portable sense as a metaphor. In his work “Poetics”, Arastu argues that the use of metaphor requires creative skill:

“...only then cannot be mastered from others, this ability serves as a sign of talent. After all, creating good metaphors means being able to see similarity” Arastu says that the ability to create metaphors equates to innate talent, which is why it cannot be mastered from others. Quintilian, on the other hand, says that it is the gift of nature that everyone uses in the same way. In his opinion, the metaphor is shrinking, enriching, giving a special shine to speech it is likeness and, taking risks, only boldly applied metaphors can give a special elevation to speech. Cicero also views metaphors as an abbreviated analogy, and says that language negates

such metaphors if there is no correspondence between the two objects obtained. In this regard, Demetrius's opinion is noteworthy: "metaphor is likability to speech and grandeur dedicates.

Problems in translating metaphors. Analyzing the importance of metaphor in translation studies, Dobrzynska notes that it has "unbelievable popularity". And Kurtz, while dwelling on this definition of Dobrzynska, does not hide his surprise that this popularity has not been sufficiently researched. Commenting on the importance of metaphor in translation studies, Menakr describes the "unspeakable" hidden meaning of metaphors as its main difficulty. In doing so, you have to take into account the culture, the history of the use of the metaphor, and other such small details. Newmark, Turi and Tabakovska in their scientific research describe metaphor as "the final test for any theory of the source being translated" for the translator. Also, in his scientific work on metaphor translation, Turi states that "we cannot generalize about metaphor translation without being speculative." Dagut, in his scientific views, explains that metaphor translation can be solved in two ways.

The first is that it cannot be translated, and the second believes that it should be translated word for word. Briefly, views on metaphor translation can be divided into three parts: a) Metaphor cannot be translated (Nida, Vinay and Darbelnet, Dagut are supporters of this idea) b) Metaphor is completely translated like other sources of translation (Kloepfer, Mason and Kurt support this idea) c) Metaphors can be translated, but cannot convey the same meaning as the original (Den Broeck, Alvarez, Turi, Newmark, Snell-Hornby, Reidman and Diges, Schaffner and Ali). According to Dobrzinska (1995), the transfer of a linguistic metaphor from one language to another "brings it to a completely different communicative situation". Dobrzynska's argument is that a metaphor becomes a new and completely different word due to a different environment, as a result of which a different meaning of the metaphor appears. Kovecses (2007) is a supporter of Lakoff and Johnson's claim that some conceptual metaphors are unique to the human mind's ability to connect with abstract concepts, and they can be called universal. He tries to explain the difference between Lakoff and Johnson's claim that conceptual metaphor is almost universal, and linguistic metaphor is infinitely varied across languages and cultures. His argument is that although conceptual metaphor can be shared across languages and cultures, conceptual metaphor can be expressed in very different ways in two languages and cultures.

In conclusion, although our language has a lot of methods and tools that serve to express ideas for a speaker or writer, in the process of speech, a willful

speaker comes to achieve his goal of communication. On the side of it, the units added Do not ensure that the goal is fully valid. In this regard, suitable for the speaker to complement the object of speech provides an opportunity to metaphorically apply the linguistic unity.

REFERENCES:

1. Sapir, E. 1956. Culture, Language and Personality. Los Angeles: University of California Press
2. Nida, E. 1964. "Principles of Correspondence." In Venuti, L. The Translation Studies Reader. London: Routledge
3. Haydarova, U., & Umarova, M. (2022). YAPON MUTOZ MANBALARIDA QO'LLANGAN METAFORALARNING TURLARI TASNIFI. Science and innovation, 1(B3), 599-603.
4. Qosimov, A. A. (2022, May). INGLIZ TILIDA OBRAZLI TIL VOSITALARI VA ULARNING KLASSIFIKATSIYASI. METAFORLARNING BOSHQA OBRAZLI TIL VOSITALARIDAN FARQI. In International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online) (Vol. 2, No. 4).
5. Newmark, P. (1988a). Approaches to Translation. London: Prentice Hall International (1st ed. 1981 Pergamon Institute of English).
6. Kosimov, A. (2022). METAFORANING O'RGANILISHIGA DOIR YONDASHUVLAR. ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ, 4(2), 114-116